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Research Article

**LEARNING STYLES OF UNDERGRADUATE MEDICAL
STUDENTS, TRENDS & IMPLICATIONS**Dr Muhammad Taha¹, Dr Gulfishan¹, Dr Hira Khalid¹

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Abstract:

Background and Definition: Learning style is an individual's unique approach to learning based on strengths, weakness and preferences. There are many different learning style models some of which are David Kolbe's model, Peter Honey and Alan Mumford's model and Neil Flemming's VARK model which is what we will be using for our research.

Material and Methods: A cross sectional study of 44 undergraduate medical students was performed. The VARK questionnaire was used to categorize the learning style of students. The questionnaire consisted of 24 items which identify four different learning styles; visual, aural, read/write and kinesthetic.

Results: Only 36% student preferred only one learning style (uni-modal), primarily kinesthetic while the remaining students chose more than one learning style (multi-modal), where only 16% were bi-modal, 39% were tri-modal and 41% were quad-modal.

Conclusion: The students in study preferred diverse multimodal learning styles which were unevenly distributed, kinesthetic being the most common and read/write as the least common. The teacher's awareness of the preferred learning style of the learner help him to match it with modes of instruction to ensure a conducive learning atmosphere for learners.

Keywords: Learning styles, trends and implications, undergraduate medical students, VARK questionnaire, academic performance.

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INTRODUCTION:

Learning is the act of acquiring new or modifying existing knowledge, behavior, skills, values and preferences. Human learning may occur as a part of education, personal development, schooling or training. There is evidence for human behavioral learning prenatally, in which habituation has been observed as early as 32 weeks into gestation. Play has been approached by several theorists as the first form of learning. Lev Vygotsky agrees that play is necessary for children's development. There is a difference in the learning style of different individuals and the theorists propose that all people can be classified according to their style of learning, although different theorist present differing views on how the styles should be classified. A common concept is that individuals differ in how they learn.

The idea of individualized learning style originated in 1970s and has greatly influenced education. The "Meshing Hypothesis" suggests that a student will learn best if taught in a method deemed appropriate for the students learning style. A 2004 literature review identified 71 different learning style theories. One of them is "David A. Kolbe's model that is based on experiential learning theory. According to Kolbe's model the ideal learning process engages four modes. i.e Concrete experience , Abstract conceptualization as well as related to approaches towards transforming experience: Reflective Observation and Active Experimentation in response to situational demands. Another one of the most common and widely used categorization of various types of learning style is Neil D. Fleming's VARK model which expanded upon Neuro-linguistic programming models.

- Visual learner
- Auditory learners;
- Kinesthetic learners or Tactile.
- Read/ Write

In 2015 a cross sectional was conducted on 194 undergraduate medical students enrolled at Shalimar Medical and Dental College Lahore. The version 7.1 of VARK questionnaire was used to classify the learning preference as visual, auditory, read/write and kinesthetic. The students were also asked to rank preferred VARK mode of learning. Only 36% students preferred one learning style (uni-modal), primarily kinesthetic while the remaining students chose more than one learning style (multi-modal), where 44% were bi-modal, 15% tri-modal and only 5% were quad-modal.

In 2014 a cohort case study was conducted on 450 undergraduate medical students enrolled at Taibah University. Using a LSQ questionnaire the students

were asked to classify their learning styles as theorist, pragmatist, activist and reflector. No single learning style predominated, 25% were reflectors, and 20% were theorists, 17% pragmatist and 19% activist. Combined reflector and theorists was the predominant bi-modal learning style in 27% students. This study looks in to the learning styles of 4th year under graduate medical students at GUJRANWALA MEDICAL COLLEGE, GUJRANWALA PAKISTAN using VARK Questionnaire. The resulting dominant single and multiple preferred learning styles are presented and their implications are analyzed. The objective of the study is to find the preferred learning modality among the students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design: Cross sectional Descriptive study

Study Population: Questions regarding the learning style were asked from the students of 4th year from Gujranwala Medical College.

Sampling technique: the sampling technique was probability sampling.

Inclusion Criteria: Medical students of GMC.

Exclusion Criteria: Medical students of other medical colleges.

Consent and Ethical issues: During the course of this study no ethical concerns are raised.

Data Collection Method:

Research is done in Gujranwala Medical College with data collected from 44 undergraduate medical students belonging to 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and final year. 35 questions with each having 2 options were asked. The students were asked to describe their learning style and the options of learning style that were given were aural (where a student learns through lectures, speech and discussions), visual (where a student learns from graphs, chart, flow diagrams) and kinesthetic (where a student learns by performing an activity). Students returned the given questionnaire with their preferred learning style and the questionnaires were evaluated and the results were concluded.

Questionnaire: A standard VARK questionnaire was used.

Response: The response rate was 100%. Out of 44 students all 44 responded.

Analysis: SPSS version 13.5 is used.

The questionnaire was filled by the students online and analyzed.

RESULTS:

The following results were obtained from data collection:

1. Demographic variables:

The demographic variable included both male and females between ages of 20-25 years from 1st to final year, day scholars as well as hostel-lite.

Age	20-25 years
Gender	Males / Females
Class	1 st year – 5 th year
Living status	Day scholar/ hostel-lite

2. Modalities of students:

The majority of the students were quad-modal following tri-modal, bimodal and then uni-modal respectively.

Frequency No of Students	VAR K Style	Percentage %
44	Uni-modal	4%
	Bi-modal	16%
	Tri-modal	39%
	Quad-modal	41%

2. Vark style:

36% chose kinesthetic style of learning while 11% choosing read and write.

Frequency No of Students	VAR K Style	Percentages %
44	Visual	30%
	Auditory	23%
	Read/Write	11%
	Kinesthetic	36%

Confounder: Teaching methodology

DISCUSSION:

This study has been carried out to gain an understanding of the learning preferences of Gujranwala Medical College students and to determine the distribution of the learning style preferences of them. In general, the findings of this study provide insight into the ways that our medical students learn in relation to the subject of study. We think our study may help to shed light on medical students learning development. We found that many students preferred to learn by more than one mode of information presentation. The VARK questionnaire is widely used by researchers to identify the learning preference of students. Learning style varies from one group to another based on culture, the nature of the studies and the characteristics of students. 30% of the students are visual learner, 23% are auditory learner, 11% are read/write and 36% are kinesthetic. Many students have chosen multiple learning styles, instead of sticking to only one. 4% are uni-modal, 16% are bimodal, 39% are tri-modal and 41% are quad-modal. In our study, kinesthetic learner shows the highest percentage of 36. Similar results had been shown in another study by Stephney Whillier 2014, in which kinesthetic learner were 65.4%. This study was done on chiopractic students. Chiopractic shown

to be largely multimodal learner (56%) with a preference for kinesthetic learning. In this study visual were 50.6%, aural were 52% and read/write were 51.6%. Multimodality had been shown in Heidi L.Lujan, Stephen E.DiCarlo 2006 studies. It was 63.8%. Quad-modal were the greatest having 43.4%, tri-modal (32.1) and then bimodal (24.5). In this study Kinesthetic were reported the highest (18.1%), Read/write (7.8), Aural (4.8), and then visual (5.4%). Visual learners should be stimulated with depictions of information in charts, graphs, flow charts, and all the symbolic arrows, circles and other devices that instructors use to represent what could have been presented in words. Auditory learning is achieved through listening during peer instruction, collaborative testing, debate, and answering questions. Manipulating models and role playing satisfies kinesthetic and tactile learners. Reading /writing learners can be approached with information depicted in words. Mary Johnson 2009 studies also depicts the same results. A vast majority of the students show Multimodality. In 2015 a cross sectional was conducted on 194 undergraduate medical students enrolled at Shalimar Medical and Dental College Lahore. The version 7.1 of VARK questionnaire was used to classify the learning preference as visual, auditory, read/write and kinesthetic. The students were also asked to rank preferred VARK mode of learning. Only 36% students preferred one learning style (uni-modal), primarily kinesthetic while the remaining students chose more than one learning style (multi-modal), where 44% were bi-modal, 15% tri-modal and only 5% were quad-modal.

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CONCLUSION:

Learning process can be facilitated and learning can be enriched by understanding preferred modes of medical students. The occurrence of different learning modalities among medical students can be addressed by choosing diverse teaching strategies. This also encourages the students to draw upon learning opportunities designed to match their own style. It also has the potential to enhance the capacity of at-risk students and improve their overall academic performance. Educational experience can be made more productive through this approach and help students in attaining success.

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